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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The EU-funded SEA-Quester project is conducting exploratory research into newly emerging European and polar blue carbon habitats. This assessment supports these efforts by evaluating how blue carbon is currently acknowledged in national and international climate and biodiversity policy frameworks using the Arctic as a case study. To accomplish this, we analysed national submissions from Arctic Council member states, observer countries, and the EU, complemented by interviews with relevant in-country representatives.

Our analysis shows that blue carbon is acknowledged more widely by observers than by member states of the Arctic Council and more often in a biodiversity (NBSAP) than in a climate (NDC) context. All interviewees agreed that multiple positive co-benefits could arise from more effective preservation and management of blue carbon ecosystems.

While the concept of blue carbon has reached the Arctic to a small extent, it was primarily associated with coastal ecosystems within international frameworks. Oceanic forms of blue carbon habitats or species that exist further from shore or in deeper waters were not mentioned or specified to a similar extent as were coastal ecosystems.

Although the climate adaptation benefits of coastal and marine ecosystems are acknowledged in scientific research, we observed that international policy frameworks place greater emphasis on their climate change mitigation potential.

We briefly explore potential reasons for these patterns, aiming to inform policymakers currently updating their national climate or biodiversity plans. We conclude with observations on science-policy gaps and offer recommended action points.

While this assessment focused on the Arctic, the Antarctic could benefit from a similar evaluation, focusing on the role of blue carbon within international policy frameworks relevant for the region to generalize our understanding of polar blue carbon.

BACKGROUND

Blue Carbon

Referring to carbon sequestration facilitated by and through living marine organisms (organic, as opposed to inorganic carbon) as “blue carbon” became popular over a decade ago (source: [Google Books “Ngram” Viewer](#)). With growing recognition that tropical coastal ecosystems like mangroves, seagrasses, and salt marshes could play a larger role in climate change mitigation ([Nelleman *et al.*, 2009](#)), countries are now encouraged to reduce emissions from their continued degradation, loss, and conversion and to conserve these important carbon stocks in the same manner as terrestrial forests and wetlands under LULUCF guidelines (Land Use, Land Use Change, and Forestry).

Recently, global discourse and scientific efforts have suggested expanding the definition of blue carbon beyond the coast to include oceanic blue carbon ([Lutz *et al.*, 2021](#); [Hilmi *et al.*, 2021](#)), such as area-based marine ecosystems like kelp forests ([McHenry *et al.*, 2025](#)) and unique benthic habitats ([James *et al.*, 2024](#)), or species-based estimates, including whales ([Pearson *et al.*, 2023](#)) and commercial fisheries ([Saba *et al.*, 2021](#) (see also the [2024 Workshop Report](#) from International Council for the Exploration of the Seas), or even large-scale processes such as the biological pump ([Nowicki *et al.*, 2022](#)) or the lipid pump ([Jónasdóttir *et al.*, 2015](#)) powered by the pelagic plankton community. Discussion is ongoing about whether these ecosystems are “amenable to management” (see entry for [“blue carbon” in the glossary](#) for the Special Report on Oceans and Cryosphere in a Changing Climate from the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change [IPCC], 2019).

While many ocean-based climate change mitigation options exist, their ability to produce co-benefits varies. However, preventing the further loss of biodiverse and carbon-rich marine habitats and providing the means to protect and restore these habitats is one of the most effective win-win solutions to address both climate change and biodiversity loss ([Smith *et al.*, 2021](#)). If managed effectively, blue carbon ecosystems can offer other co-benefits, like climate adaptation and resilience (like coastal protection), supporting a sustainable blue economy (like food security or job creation), or accessing needed financial development capital through public funding or private carbon markets ([Armstrong *et al.*, 2019](#); [Bax *et al.*, 2021](#)). Social co-benefits are also possible but understudied and often overlooked ([Pascual *et al.*, 2022](#)).

Blue Carbon in the Polar Regions

Polar regions are unique both in terms of the types of ecosystems that might be considered blue carbon and in the nature of carbon sequestration processes that occur.

In high-latitude marine waters, kelp forests and eelgrass are often cited as examples of coastal blue carbon habitats. However, oceanic blue carbon (certain species like krill or

mesopelagic fish), as well as pelagic and benthic ecosystems (such as mussel or maerl beds), are also worth considering. Box 1 shows the diverse species and habitats encompassed by blue carbon in the polar regions. Yet, these ecosystems are changing rapidly due to significant physical, geochemical, and biological shifts. Furthermore, polar ecosystems are experiencing the emergence and expansion of entirely novel marine ecosystems, driven by new environmental conditions and the co-occurrence of species not previously found together.

Examples of the aforementioned geochemical, physical, and biological changes, both temperatures ([Holland & Bitz, 2003](#)) and ocean acidification (see [Nissen et al., 2025](#) for observations from the Antarctic; see [Qi et al., 2024](#) for estimates from the Arctic) are accelerating in the polar regions faster than the global average. Tropical/boreal marine species are expanding poleward (“borealization”, [Fossheim et al., 2015](#) or “Atlantification” [Polyakov et al., 2025](#)), and the timing of annually recurring events (phenology shifts) is shifting, alongside threats like the influx of freshwater and coastal darkening from glacier melt, and de-oxygenation.

It remains uncertain whether the climate-induced expansion of both current and emerging novel ecosystems (“seaforestation”) will increase natural carbon stocks as oceans warm and sea-ice retreats, coupled with the potential loss of current carbon-rich ecosystems. This is especially relevant for the Arctic, due to the loss of sea ice ([März et al., 2022](#)). The IPCC Special Report on Changing Ocean Marine Ecosystems projects a decrease in the upper ocean export of organic carbon to the deep-sea floor by 2090 (medium confidence, [Bindoff et al., 2019](#)), but enough regional uncertainty exists to warrant further research (see [Buessler et al., 2020](#) and [Jin et al., 2020](#) for the biological carbon pump in particular), including in the polar regions, where it might even increase.

Locating, quantifying, and understanding the current extent of blue carbon stocks in the polar regions serves as an important baseline. To account for emerging novel ecosystems and the rapid pace of change, this knowledge needs to be coupled with an improved understanding of residence time (how long those stocks are viable) and best-available projections of change for existing and emerging “polar blue carbon” ecosystems under different climate scenarios.

“For marine ecosystems the carbon pools and sequestration rates have only been examined in detail for a small number of habitat types. Seagrass beds, for example, have been the focus of the largest number of studies (55) whereas there is far less information on carbon sequestration and storage on the large number of benthic habitats associated with different subtidal sediments.” -[Mapping and Assessment of Ecosystems and their Services: An EU ecosystem assessment \(2020\)](#)

Box 1: What might “polar blue carbon” look like?

Be sure to check out the [OSPAR Commission Habitats Webpage](#) for more information! Image credits (under the [CC-BY-SA 4.0 license](#)) and thanks to the Institute for Marine Research (IMR; Havforskninginstituttet) [Media Library](#). A) Maerl Bed at St Austell Bay. Credit: © Natural England/Hazel Selley. Available on Flickr. See also [Ruglbunn](#); B) Antarctic Krill. (Cecilie Thorsen Broms); C) Eelgrass. (Espen Bierdu); D) Flat oysters and mussels. Tvedestrand. GOPRO. (Espen Bierdu); E) *Calanus finmarchius*; F) Capelin shoal from CRISP expedition. (Maria Tenningen); G) Kelp. (Jonas Thormar); H) Paragorgia and cauliflower coral on Lophelia coral reef (Mareano).

Limitations of Blue Carbon

Numerous challenges make it difficult to comprehensively quantify carbon sequestration from either oceanic or coastal blue carbon, and consequently, to manage these systems to maximize climate change mitigation through nature-based solutions (NbS; [Christianson et al., 2022](#)). The polar marine environment is no exception.

This Assessment doesn't address the equivalency or comparative value of "polar blue carbon" when it comes to prioritizing climate actions (see also [Figure SPM7](#) from the IPCC – Overview of Mitigation Options to compare; [Dhakal et al., 2022](#)). While important to reduce emissions resulting from ecosystem degradation through conservation, the overall contribution of blue carbon is small compared to the scale of anthropogenic emissions (differing by several orders of magnitude; [Macreadie et al., 2021](#)), a point that is also outlined in the IPCC Special Report on Changing Ocean Marine Ecosystems ([Bindoff et al., 2019](#)).

In addition to challenges to accurately quantify carbon sequestration (Box 2), there are large uncertainties in estimating the cost-effectiveness and area effectiveness of blue carbon interventions ([Williamson & Gattuso, 2022](#)). Nature-based solutions to protect or enhance blue carbon beyond the coasts, such as avoiding benthic disturbances like

Box 2: Sequestration

SEA-Quester defines this important term as any carbon stored within a reservoir out of contact with the atmosphere. The IPCC defines carbon sequestration simply as: "The process of storing carbon in a carbon pool."

This is very similar to the 2019 IPCC definition, which reads, "The long-term removal of carbon dioxide (CO₂) or other forms of carbon from the atmosphere, with secure storage on climatically significant time scales (decadal to century). The period of storage needs to be known for climate modelling and carbon accounting purposes."

In broad terms, this is controlled by the flux of carbon into the reservoir and the mean residence time of carbon within the reservoir. At steady state, the blue carbon content of any given reservoir is a product of these two values. Changes in the balance over time could reflect changes in either value or expansion of the reservoir's physical extent.

In voluntary carbon markets, the definition of "permanence" in long-term project contracts typically ranges from 3 to 100 years ([Miltenberger et al., 2021](#)), but fully considering the balance between past and present residence times and flux (i.e. carbon sequestered in the geologic past which has now reached the end of its residence time) means conservation and restoration activities might not be suited to offset fossil fuel emissions ([Visser, 2024](#)).

bottom trawling, ocean animal biomass restoration, or setting catch limits on oceanic mesopelagic fish, had both the highest scientific uncertainty and lowest projected impact on climate when compared to terrestrial solutions, based on expert interviews ([Buma et al., 2024](#)). Consequently, addressing knowledge gaps may mean some of these pathways have a higher or lower potential than initially estimated. It can be argued that a focus on enhancing sinks or nature-based solutions might detract or distract from critical emissions reduction efforts ([Johannessen & Christian et al., 2023](#)).

Projects such as EU-funded [SEA-Quester](#), [POMP](#), and [C-Blues](#) are actively working to identify and quantify the most significant blue carbon hotspots in temperate and polar latitudes, which can inform if and how these ecosystems can fit within existing mitigation frameworks and better incorporate carbon benefits into regional preservation and management decision-making.

Blue Carbon in International Policy Frameworks

The potential and relevance of blue carbon for greenhouse gas removals have received increased attention over the years, leading to its gradual recognition within the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) process and the Paris Agreement. At the same time, the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) offers another relevant avenue for blue carbon – as both a conservation and climate issue – for policy consideration at the international level ([Thoni & Rummukainen, 2025](#)).

United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC)

Under the UNFCCC, all Parties shall promote the sustainable management of natural carbon sinks and reservoirs, including those from “...oceans as well as other coastal and marine ecosystems,” (Article 4. Paragraph 1 (d)). Additionally, Parties are required to inventory natural carbon sinks of all greenhouse gases (Article 4 Paragraph 1 (a)).

In the UNFCCC context, “mitigation” refers to efforts to reduce emissions AND enhance sinks. The UNFCCC further defines “any process, activity, or mechanism which removes a greenhouse gas (GHG), aerosol, or precursor from the atmosphere” as a sink, although the non-permanence and potential reversibility of natural carbon stocks has long been acknowledged concerning terrestrial efforts to reduce emissions from Land Use, Land Use Change and Forestry (LULUCF) sector (i.e. land conversion or deforestation).

[Vanderklift et al. \(2022\)](#) reviewed a subset of UNFCCC mechanisms and tools relevant to the protection and restoration of coastal blue carbon ecosystems, which included Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs), REDD+ (Reducing emissions from deforestation and forest degradation), and national GHG inventories. They conclude that GHG inventories are likely to create a variety of incentives for enhancing protection, better management, and restoration of blue carbon ecosystems, while NDCs can be

used to communicate this as well as other commitments through the framework of the Paris Agreement.

National Inventory Submissions (NIS) utilize guidelines and methodologies provided by the IPCC to quantify natural carbon stocks in wetlands, forests, and other carbon-rich ecosystems at risk of loss. However, including these ecosystems is only encouraged, not mandatory. Some member states and scientists have indicated a desire to expand national inventories to account for a higher diversity of natural carbon sinks, including from marine ecosystems. For example, Japan's 2024 National Inventory Document (part of its National Inventory Report, which collectively represents its official GHG inventory) adapted the IPCC wetland methodology to include sequestration from kelp forests and seagrasses ([Ministry of Environment Japan, 2024](#)).

This assessment focuses on NDCs as the key mechanism of the Paris Agreement to achieve its long-term goals. Each Party prepares, communicates, and maintains successive nationally determined contributions (NDCs) that it intends to achieve. Article 4.3 requires a progressive “ratcheting up” of commitments listed in NDCs every 5 to 10 years (called a “bottom-up” approach).

In total, 65 countries recognise coastal blue carbon ecosystems by including the conservation or restoration of mangroves, seagrasses, and/or saltmarshes as mitigation components of their new or updated NDCs ([Lecerf, M. et al. 2023](#)). However, there is a high diversity of reporting formats, both within and between NDCs ([Laurans, 2016](#); [Pauw et al., 2018](#)), which could be considered both a strength and a weakness of the “bottom-up” approach and for drawing common baselines on novel and emerging issues.

Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD)

In 2020, the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) approved a global framework with the goal of living in harmony with nature by 2050. Sometimes called the “Paris Agreement for Nature” but officially the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework (KMGBF), this includes four overarching goals to achieve the 2050 vision, along with 23 targets to achieve by 2030. National Biodiversity Strategy & Action Plans (NBSAPs, sometimes referred to as “N-B-Saps”) are the principal instrument for Parties to implement actions to reach KMGBF targets at the national and global level, and are required under Article 6 of the Convention ([NBSAP Capacity Building Module 1, 2011](#)). Although periodic updating and revision are recommended, it is not strictly required.

KMGBF targets provide a major impetus for ecosystem protection and restoration, offering a robust path to safeguard biodiversity, with the potential to deliver climate benefits. Achieving the KMGBF targets for blue carbon ecosystems could contribute 2.8% of the reduction of carbon emissions needed to limit anthropogenic warming to 2 °C by 2030 ([Fu et al., 2024](#)). Assessing, mapping, and conserving these habitats could

help reach multiple targets under the KMGBF; this policy assessment focused on Targets 1, 2, 3, 8, and 11 (Table 1).

Table 1: KMGBF Targets and Indicators Potentially Relevant for Blue Carbon in the Polar Regions (taken from <https://www.cbd.int/gbf/targets>)

	Description	Headline Indicators
Target 1	<p>Plan and Manage all Areas To Reduce Biodiversity Loss</p> <p><i>Ensure that all areas are under participatory, integrated, and biodiversity inclusive spatial planning and/or effective management processes addressing land and sea use change, to bring the loss of areas of high biodiversity important, including ecosystems of high ecological integrity, close to zero by 2030, while respecting the rights of indigenous peoples and local communities.</i></p>	<p>A.1 Red List of Ecosystems</p> <p>A.2 Extent of natural ecosystems</p> <p>1.1 Per cent of land and seas covered by biodiversity-inclusive spatial plans*</p>
Target 2	<p>Restore 30% of all Degraded Ecosystems</p> <p><i>Ensure that by 2030 at least 30 per cent of areas of degraded terrestrial inland water, and coastal and marine ecosystems are under effective restoration, in order to enhance biodiversity and ecosystem functions and services, ecological integrity and connectivity.</i></p>	<p>2.2 Area under restoration</p>
Target 3	<p>Conserve 30% of Land, Waters and Seas</p> <p><i>Ensure and enable that by 2030 at least 30 per cent of terrestrial, inland water, and coastal and marine areas, especially areas of particular importance for biodiversity and ecosystem functions and services, are effectively conserved and managed through ecologically representative, well-connected and equitably governed systems of protected areas and other effective area-based conservation measures, recognizing indigenous and traditional territories where applicable, and integrated into wider landscapes, seascapes and the ocean, while ensuring that any sustainable use where appropriate in such areas, is fully consistent with conservation outcomes,</i></p>	<p>3.1 Coverage of protected areas and OECMs</p>

	Description	Headline Indicators
	<i>recognizing and respecting the rights of indigenous peoples and local communities, including over their traditional territories.</i>	
Target 8	<p>Minimize the Impacts of Climate Change on Biodiversity and Build Resilience</p> <p><i>Minimize the impact of climate change and ocean acidification on biodiversity and increase its resilience through mitigation, adaptation, and disaster risk reduction actions, including through nature-based solution and/or ecosystem-based approaches, while minimizing negative and fostering positive impacts of climate action on biodiversity.</i></p>	NONE
Target 11	<p>Restore, Maintain and Enhance Nature’s Contributions to People</p> <p><i>Restore, maintain and enhance nature’s contributions to people, including ecosystem functions and services, such as regulation of air, water, and climate, soil health, pollination and reduction of disease risk, as well as protection from natural hazards and disasters, through nature-based solutions and/or ecosystem-based approaches for the benefit of all people and nature.</i></p>	B.1 Services provided by ecosystems*

Target 1: Effective, participatory, integrated, and biodiversity-inclusive spatial planning, is arguably the most important prerequisite for meeting all other targets. Marine spatial planning (MSP) is an inclusive process that sets the foundation for completing environmental impact assessments, prioritizing management actions, and mobilizing funds and resources. Good MSP processes balance competing interests, potential stakeholder conflicts, and the diverse values and types of use that come from the increasing demands society places on the ocean. Despite high levels of acceptance and widespread use, significant hurdles remain to the successful implementation of MSP ([Santos et al., 2021](#)).

Areas of high carbon sequestration might be included in “areas of high ecological integrity” under Target 1, depending on the level of intactness and climate vulnerability. Relevant indicators under this Target include the number of countries using ocean accounts or natural capital accounts in their planning processes. Carbon-rich

ecosystems might also fall under “important habitats to be located within marine protected areas or integrated marine and coastal area management”.

Targets 2 and 3 refer to restoring and conserving 30% of all ecosystems by 2030, respectively. Target 2 does not require areas to be restored (since this takes a long time) but does require that “effective restoration activities” are initiated in degraded coastal and marine ecosystems. Importantly, these activities can be undertaken to enhance ecosystem functions and services, such as carbon sequestration. Target 3 is commonly referred to as “30x30” or “30 by 30” because it requires a fixed quantity of all land and seas to be conserved or protected. This target also calls for the expansion and enhancement of “areas of particular importance for biodiversity and ecosystem services.” However, area-based conservation measures may not benefit all “polar blue carbon” ecosystems ([K Filbee-Dexter et al., 2024](#)).

Target 8 aims to “minimize the impacts of climate change and ocean acidification on biodiversity” and to build resilience through climate mitigation and adaptation, including ecosystem-based approaches. “Ecosystem-based mitigation” is further defined as actions that enhance or restore ecosystem services such as carbon storage and sequestration in support of climate mitigation activities, while avoiding unintentional or otherwise negative impacts to biodiversity. This target includes language specifying that vulnerability to climate change should be considered when determining protected and conserved area boundaries, relevant for current polar blue carbon sequestration hotspots that are threatened. One of the indicators listed to help Parties effectively report on progress towards Target 8 is the total climate regulation services provided by ecosystems, categorized by ecosystem type (following the UN System of Environmental Economic Accounts, [UN-SEEA](#)).

Under Target 11, the provision and regulation of clean air, water, and a safe climate should be restored, maintained, and enhanced by 2030. Like Target 8, it lists that these can be accomplished in part through nature-based solutions and/or ecosystem-based approaches. This target also has a mandatory or Headline indicator (B.1 Services provided by ecosystems) relevant for polar blue carbon.

METHODS AND APPROACH

We used the Arctic as a case study to evaluate how blue carbon is acknowledged in documents submitted under the Paris Agreement and the Convention of Biological Diversity, complemented by interviews with national public authorities.

Document Analysis

We analysed Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs) and National Biodiversity Strategies & Action Plans (NBSAPs), documents that countries use to communicate specific goals and targets in line with their international commitments to address climate change and nature loss, respectively. The “Background” section has more details.

The analysis is based on a systematic review of selected NDCs and NBSAPs of member and observer states to the Arctic Council¹, including the European Union. The chosen approach to defining the “Arctic” differs from a purely ecological or geographic perspective but was considered optimal for investigating the awareness and potential of blue carbon among states engaged in the region through their formal participation in the Arctic Council, which functions as a regional intergovernmental forum.

This approach has limitations regarding blue carbon in the Arctic, as it includes Observers that lack a marine border (Switzerland), or belong to various geographical regions (non-Arctic Europe and Asia). However, this methodology allows for insights that extend beyond the immediate region, offering a broader picture of the current state and strategies related to blue carbon. In total, the analysis covers 22 current and former Parties to the Paris Agreement² and the Convention on Biological Diversity.

Content analysis was chosen as a research method to study these documents, as it enables the examination of texts and communications to uncover patterns, themes, or biases. The design of content analysis was inspired by [Krippendorff \(2019\)](#), who defines content analysis as a research technique for making replicable and valid inferences from texts (or other meaningful matter) to contexts of their use. Despite several advantages of the method, it is limited to the quality of source materials, contextual information, and potential bias of the analyst(s).

In total, twelve (12) NDCs and eight (8) NBSAPs were included in the analysis. Sources are listed in Appendix A: Overview of NDCs and NBSAPs. NVivo, a qualitative data analysis software, was used to facilitate management, analysis, and systematisation of the qualitative data documents.

¹ <https://arctic-council.org/about/states/>
<https://arctic-council.org/about/observers/>

² On January 20, 2025, the United States of America withdrew for a second time from the Paris Agreement under the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change. However, the USA remains a Party to the UNFCCC.

Only the most recent available NDCs and NBSAPs submitted in English were included. The 12 NDCs correspond to 21 Parties (current and former) to the Paris Agreement (the European Union and its member states submit a joint NDC), covering all member and observer states of the Arctic Council, except China, whose original submission is available only in Chinese. Of the 22 Parties in this analysis, only six have submitted an “NDCs 3.0” and only 15 have submitted NBSAPs, seven of which are in languages other than English (and thus excluded from the analysis).

The document analysis was guided by the following research questions:

1. *Does the NDC reference blue carbon? If so, how?*
2. *Does the NBSAP reference blue carbon? If so, how?*

We also posed the following questions about research and development surrounding coastal or marine blue carbon:

1. *How does the NDC communicate about research and development (R&D) for blue carbon?*
2. *How does the NBSAP communicate about research and development (R&D) for blue carbon?*

For the analysis of each submission type (NDC and NBSAP), we developed an analytical framework, reflecting the key focus areas and the nature of submissions. The analytical framework for NDCs consisted of 3 categories: Mitigation, Adaptation, and Research & Development. The analytical framework for NBSAPs comprised 6 categories: Target 1, Target 2, Target 3, Target 8, Target 11, and Research & Development.

If language on blue carbon was included in NDCs, we further categorized passages as a reference to Mitigation or Adaptation, Research & Development. If blue carbon was referenced in NBSAPs, we further categorized the passage into one of the five KM-GBF targets selected for this analysis: Target 1, Target 2, Target 3, Target 8, Target 11, and/or Research & Development. This sub-categorization was based on a keyword search, critical examination of the published content, and internal review by GRID-Arendal.

Complementary Interviews

Interviews were conducted to complement the document analysis based on the availability of interviewees during the project timeline. We prioritized contacting people directly employed in or by national government ministries and agencies involved with NDC or NBSAP development. Three interviews were completed with representatives from Canada, Finland, and the Republic of Korea (ROK). Additional potential interviewees were contacted but had limited capacity to respond at the time of writing. This assessment can be updated to include their additional insights and contributions later, as their schedule allows.

A semi-structured approach (Ayres, 2008) was used (questionnaire available in Appendix C) to allow for conversations around perceived barriers and gaps to their inclusion of blue carbon and emerging novel ecosystems in existing policy instruments and governance frameworks. Any inconsistencies or ambiguities that arose were subject to adjustment between and during interviews. If ambiguities emerged, selected interviewees were contacted for clarification or supplementary insights to strengthen the validity of the report. Interviews were transcribed through MS Teams AI assistant, which was then reviewed by the GRID-Arendal interviewer. Interviewees were also given the option to respond to parts of the questionnaire in writing to accommodate busy schedules, time zone differences, and assist with translations of certain terms, if needed.

Informed consent was obtained from all participants before their engagement. This was via written, informed, prior consent received by email, and through a verbal agreement during the recording. To protect the privacy of the individuals contacted and encourage open reflection, all personal data was gathered and stored according to the GRID-Arendal Privacy Policy, the EU GDPR, and Norwegian law. This Assessment and any public accompanying materials based on the findings will not disclose the names of individuals. The survey responses will be anonymized and aggregated to the level of country. Participants can, at any time, withdraw their participation in the project and request that associated data be deleted (cf. the GDPR's right to be forgotten).

FINDINGS

Key Document Findings:

1. None of the Arctic Council member states refer to “blue carbon” or “marine carbon” in their NDC submission.
2. Of the 12 NDCs available, only 2 Arctic Council observer states – Singapore and the UK acknowledge blue carbon and marine carbon sequestration in their NDC (3.0).
3. Of the 8 NBSAPs available, only 1 Arctic member state – Canada – and 2 observers to the Arctic Council – Japan and the Republic of Korea – acknowledged blue carbon in their submissions.
4. Discrepancies exist between submissions from the same countries. For example, while the UK acknowledges blue carbon in its NDC, it does not include this term in its NBSAP. Conversely, Canada, Japan, and the Republic of Korea refer to blue carbon in their NBSAPs but do not recognise it in their NDCs.
5. Countries with a high percentage of national coastline were more likely to mention “blue carbon” and “ocean” in both their NDC and NBSAP submissions.

Figure 1: Country Comparison by % of Coastline

A) Comparison of the percentage of countries that acknowledge “blue carbon” and “ocean” in their NDC, grouped by the percentage of their total perimeter that is coastline. Categories are: “Mention”, “Do Not Mention”, and “Unknown” (not available in English). For supporting tables, see Appendix B.

B) Comparison of the percentage of countries that acknowledge “blue carbon” and “ocean” in their NBSAP, grouped by the percentage of their total perimeter that is coastline. Categories are: “Mention”, “Do Not Mention”, “Not Available” (not available in English), and “Unknown” (NBSAP not submitted). For supporting tables, see Appendix B.

Figure 2: Mentions of “Blue Carbon” and “Ocean” in NDCs by Country

Sankey diagrams illustrating countries by their affiliation with the Arctic Council (members, observers, or other/not affiliated) and whether their NDC explicitly references “blue carbon” or “ocean”. Each flow connects a country to one of three categories: “Mention”, “Do not mention”, or “Unknown”. For supporting tables, see Appendix B. Graph produced at www.sankeymatic.com.

A) Acknowledgement of “blue carbon” in NDCs, mapped against affiliation with the Arctic Council.

B) Acknowledgement of “ocean” in NDCs, mapped against affiliation with the Arctic Council.

Figure 3: Mentions of “Blue Carbon” and “Ocean” in NBSAPs by Country

Sankey diagrams illustrating countries by their affiliation with the Arctic Council (as members, observers, or other/not affiliated) and whether their NBSAP explicitly references “blue carbon” or “ocean”. Each flow connects a country to one of three categories: “Mention”, “Do not mention” or “Unknown”. For supporting tables, see Appendix B. Graph produced at www.sankeymatic.com.

A) Acknowledgement of “blue carbon” in NBSAPs, mapped against affiliation in the Arctic Council.

B) Acknowledgement of “ocean” in NBSAPs, mapped against affiliation in the Arctic Council.

Blue Carbon in NDCs

Our analysis revealed that out of 21 countries included in the assessment, only two Observers of the Arctic Council – the UK and Singapore – mention ‘blue carbon’ and ‘marine carbon sequestration’ in their latest NDC submissions (“NDC 3.0”) (Figure 2). Countries with a high percentage of national coastline (>90%) were more likely to mention “blue carbon” in their NDCs (Figure 1A). Countries with coastlines representing at least half of their national perimeter (but less than 90%) did not mention “blue carbon” at all in their submissions (Figure 1A).

The UK informed about activities in Jersey, Guernsey, The Isle of Man, and Scotland and their efforts to advance knowledge about blue carbon sequestration and improve blue carbon management.

Jersey’s Carbon Neutral Roadmap sets an ambition to promote Jersey as a centre of excellence for blue carbon sequestration.

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Guernsey aims to publish a marine spatial plan by the end of 2025, which will include setting out the sustainable use of the island’s marine environment and informing the potential for marine carbon sequestration.

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The Isle of Man’s ‘The Manx Blue Carbon Project’ began in 2022, working with Bangor and Swansea Universities, as well as with the UK National Oceanography Centre to research and map blue carbon stores in the Isle of Man territorial sea. The project aims to develop a comprehensive blue carbon management plan to maximise carbon sequestration and maintain and restore related biodiversity and wider ecosystem services.

p. 40-41

New evidence is also being delivered through the Scottish Blue Carbon Forum, building upon actions set out in the second Scottish Climate Change Adaptation Programme to address Scotland’s marine climate risks.

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Singapore mentioned blue carbon in the context of providing technical assistance to Small Island Developing States (SIDS) which includes customised courses on blue carbon and digitalisation.

In May 2024, Singapore launched the “SIDS of Change” technical assistance package, which aims to better equip Small Island Developing States (SIDS) to achieve a more resilient and prosperous future and includes customised courses on blue carbon and digitalisation.

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To assess mitigation and adaptation actions in the marine environment relevant to blue carbon as well as to investigate whether blue carbon was recognised in coastal or oceanic context, we expanded our research to examine how countries acknowledge marine and coastal ecosystems, marine and coastal habitats, and coastal wetlands in their NDCs.

We found that Canada, the Republic of Korea, United States, and the United Kingdom recognize the role of marine and coastal ecosystems more generally in climate change mitigation. This is supported by their commitments to conservation and restoration goals, the application of nature-based solutions, the enhancement of carbon sinks, and the integration of ecosystem values into legislation.

...consistent with the global goal to halt and reverse deforestation and forest degradation by 2030, and conserve and restore other terrestrial and marine ecosystems, launching plans to conserve, connect and restore at least 30 percent of its lands and waters by 2030, including by conserving and restoring all old-growth forests across the National Forest System.

p.25 (US)

A focus on Canada’s excess emissions brings to the fore the role of negative emissions or activities that remove carbon dioxide from the atmosphere. Carbon dioxide removal options include nature-based solutions such as afforestation and the restoration of forests, soils, and coastal ecosystems, as well as more early-stage technology-based solutions like bioenergy with carbon capture, direct air capture, enhanced rock weathering, carbon mineralization and ocean-based removal.

p. 34 (Canada)

Carbon sinks (LULUCF): The Republic of Korea will maintain and improve its carbon sinks with sustainable forest management, conservation and restoration and increase forestlands by greening urban spaces. Other options

include creating new coastal and inland wetlands as well as vegetation in waterfront areas.

p. 3 (Republic of Korea)

Approximately 90% of saltmarsh and 70% of seagrass habitats in the UK are within marine protected areas. Coastal and marine habitats such as these play an important role in supporting mitigation of and adaptation to climate change. We have embedded in law their value as wildlife rich habitats in the Environment Act and our focus is on ensuring these are effectively protected.

p. 38 (UK)

The United Kingdom's NDC appears to be the only submission that explicitly acknowledged the role of marine and coastal ecosystems in climate change adaptation. The limited recognition of the role of marine and coastal ecosystems, including blue carbon, in climate change adaptation underscores the need for scientific research to provide further evidence on effective, large-scale adaptation measures in these landscapes. Furthermore, there is no clear differentiation between coastal and oceanic blue carbon in NDC submissions, which indicates either limited awareness or a lack of detailed guidance on how to incorporate it into national climate strategies.

Blue Carbon in NBSAPs

Based on the analysis of eight available NBSAPs, it was identified that only three countries, one Arctic state – Canada – and two observers to the Arctic Council – Japan and the Republic of Korea – acknowledged “blue carbon” in their submissions (Figure 3). As with NDCs, countries were increasingly likely to mention “blue carbon” in their NBSAPs as the percentage of national coastline increased (Figure 1B).

Both Canada and the Republic of Korea reported blue carbon in achieving Target 8 in their national plans. Canada highlighted that blue carbon requires additional research and informed that the governmental bodies are undertaking projects to estimate the extent of blue carbon across Canada's three oceans in pursuit of advancing science and knowledge to minimize the impact of climate change and ocean acidification on biodiversity.

Understanding which ecosystems have high carbon sequestration potential, particularly those with irrecoverable carbon, like peatlands, can support the identification and prioritization of protected and conserved areas that mitigate climate change while also supporting biodiversity. In particular, the carbon sequestration potential of oceans and coastal ecosystems (blue carbon)

requires further research. Additional research is needed to better understand the impacts of climate change on biodiversity and how to increase nature's resilience to climate change.

p.58

DFO and NSERC are also undertaking projects to estimate the extent of blue carbon in salt marshes, seagrasses, kelp forests, and soft sediments across Canada's three oceans.

p.59

It is also important to note that Canada's NBSAP is the only submission that potentially acknowledges oceanic blue carbon, specifically referencing "oceans and coastal ecosystems" and "soft sediments across Canada's three oceans".

The Republic of Korea recognised the importance of blue carbon ecosystems in enhancing the ocean's carbon sink capacity and meeting the NDC commitment target. Additionally, the Republic of Korea indicated the intention to develop technologies for Blue Carbon-Based Climate-Adaptive Coastal Infrastructure.

Protect and restore blue carbon ecosystems to enhance the ocean's carbon sink capacity by creating salt marshes and marine forests, restoring tidal flats and increasing the coverage of protected areas. This approach will enable the ROK to meet its nationally determined contributions target of maintaining ocean carbon absorption at 1.06 million metric tons by 2030.

p.42

Develop technologies for Blue Carbon-Based Climate-Adaptive Coastal Infrastructure from 2022 to 2026, and build a database to assess the distribution and the sink capacity of blue carbon ecosystems across the country.

p.42

Japan took a broader approach to blue carbon, recognizing its potential in restoration, the application of nature-based solutions, and climate change mitigation. This is also reflected in references to blue carbon throughout different sections of the NBSAP report — including the Strategy, Action Plan, and 30by30 Roadmap.

With the aim of reducing the burden on biodiversity and promoting the application of nature-based solutions in the Strategy, the government of Japan committed to the conservation and restoration of seaweed beds, tidal flats, and coral reefs, which store blue carbon.

The government will promote the conservation, restoration, and creation of marine environment such as seaweed beds, tidal flats, and coral reefs, which play a vital role in the utilization of blue carbon as sinks and in the propagation of fishery resources.

p.35

In coastal ecosystems, the government will promote the conservation and restoration of seaweed beds and tidal flats that function as sequestration sink or storage of blue carbon, as well as wetlands that store carbon from natural sources.

p.41

To achieve the targets outlined in the Strategy, Japan recognises the potential of blue carbon ecosystems as a new alternative for sinks in the Action Plan. The specific measures to be taken in this regard are research on quantitative evaluation methods for climate change mitigation functions using blue carbon as well as efforts to create, restore, and conserve seaweed beds and tidal flats.

Additionally, carbon uptake by marine ecosystems, so-called blue carbon, is coming to international attention as a new alternative for sinks. Examples of marine ecosystems that immobilize carbon (blue carbon ecosystems) include seagrass beds, sea algae beds, wetlands and tidal flats, and mangrove forests, and studies are being conducted to evaluate these ecosystems.

p.132

The government will promote surveys and research on quantitative evaluation methods for climate change mitigation functions using carbon sequestration and storage (blue carbon) in oceans. In addition, efforts will be made to tackle the creation, restoration, and conservation of seaweed beds and tidal flats, and others.

p.135

In the 30x30 Roadmap that sets out the path to achieve 30by30 target by 2030, Japan recognises a potential role of blue carbon in synergies with climate action and points out expectation related to advancing the knowledge about blue carbon ecosystems and their mitigation potential.

Additionally, in NDCs (nationally determined contributions) based on the Paris Agreement, numerous countries addressed the absorption of CO₂ by marine ecosystems and coastal wetland ecosystems (blue carbon). Currently, although only two countries, the United States and Australia, have actually incorporated blue carbon into their national GHG inventories, it is expected that incorporating emission reductions and absorption through blue carbon will be significantly advanced.

p.230

Ecosystems such as salt marshes and seagrass beds that have sediment bottoms in coastal areas are called as blue carbon ecosystems. As knowledge is being accumulated, recently there has been a growing interest in such ecosystems as a new CO₂ sink. The Special Report on Oceans and Cryosphere released by the IPCC in 2019 also evaluated that the climate change mitigation potential of blue carbon (onsite carbon sequestration through coastal wetland plant ecosystems) around the world would be about 0.5% of worldwide GHG emissions, and thus the assessment of the effectiveness of blue carbon is currently underway.

p.232

Insights from Interviews

The complementary interviews provided additional insights and supported some findings of the document analysis.

Climate & Biodiversity

Despite a consensus in the current research that blue carbon presents both climate and biodiversity benefits, interviews revealed that countries' perceptions of incorporating blue carbon into policy or management frameworks vary and might favour one over the other. The three interviewees acknowledged multiple, positive co-benefits of blue carbon, with all three agreeing on climate change adaptation, marine-based food security, and positive effects on marine biodiversity, but placed different emphasis on climate or biodiversity benefits. This could also be due to the individual interviewee's departmental mandate.

Blue carbon was perceived as highly relevant for Finland's NBSAP, compliance with EU regulations (the restoration target and new EU restoration law in particular), management of important benthic habitats, establishing MPAs (including an ongoing

climate-smart MPA program), and integrated coastal zone management. Climate mitigation or adaptation was listed as a potential co-benefit with limitations (based also on available data for certain species). The Republic of Korea, while acknowledging biodiversity co-benefits, placed more emphasis on how blue carbon can help achieve national climate commitments (such as the [2050 Carbon Neutral Strategy](#) of the ROK). Canada acknowledged blue carbon could be related to multiple KMGBF targets and is highly relevant for NBSAPs, but the current NDC did not have a strong marine focus, although discussions during the recent UN Ocean Conference (held June 2025) highlighted the ocean-climate connection more prominently.

Evaluations of the degree of difficulty in incorporating blue carbon into existing management frameworks varied greatly based on national context and are summarised in the Table 2. The responses identified kelp forest management, MPA creation or management, and marine spatial planning as “easy” or “potentially easy” to incorporate, although there was no consensus among all three interviewees.

Table 2: Perceived difficulty* of incorporating blue carbon into existing policy or management frameworks, by number of respondents

Ocean Policies & Management Frameworks	
Fisheries Management	
Management of Marine Benthic Habitats	
Kelp Forests	<i>Not Relevant</i>
Biodiversity Beyond National Jurisdiction (BBNJ)	<i>Not Relevant</i>
National Biodiversity Strategy & Action Plan (NBSAP)**	
Marine Protected Areas (MPAs)	
Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs)**	
Marine Spatial Planning (MSP) or Integrated Coastal Zone Management (ICZM)	

Information collected through complementary interviews and based on individual assessment

**Responses to the question, “IF highly OR somewhat relevant, how difficult will it be to incorporate the value of polar blue carbon into those marine management and ocean policies within your country/region?” Areas where at least one respondent indicated the framework was not relevant and areas where at least one respondent indicated they did not know are also shown.*

***For cases when either NBSAPs or NDCs were already submitted, this question focused on perceived difficulty of implementation, rather than perceived relevance to development.*

Other relevant regional frameworks identified by Republic of Korea included the Northwest Pacific Action Plan ([NOWPAP](#)) facilitated by UNEP. Other relevant sub-national frameworks listed by Canada included National Marine Conservation Areas or other provincially designated conservation areas.

Adaptation & Mitigation

The ambiguity of blue carbon as an adaptation or mitigation measure was supported by our interview with Finland, where the potential role of blue carbon in either climate adaptation or climate mitigation was unclear. For Canada, blue carbon was flagged as potentially important in ongoing climate adaptation and mitigation efforts, with more emphasis on mitigation but also more hesitancy (especially about the role of marine carbon credits). The Republic of Korea also stressed that both mitigation and adaptation efforts were being actively pursued.

Distinction between Oceanic & Coastal Blue Carbon

Coastal or semi-coastal habitats such as kelp forests or eelgrass were most often discussed, with benthic environments also receiving some mention. Kelp forest ecosystems (*Laminaria* & *Undaria* spp) are being expanded through both aquaculture and restoration initiatives in the Republic of Korea, with expected benefits to fishery production and carbon sequestration. This is in line with other efforts in the Republic of Korea (ROK) to enhance carbon sequestration in other coastal blue carbon ecosystems, such as tidal flats and salt marshes.

Species-based blue carbon concepts (such as carbon sequestered by fish or whales), perhaps because they are beyond national jurisdiction or currently lack robust data, came up in conversation rarely or when prompted. Blue carbon data was perceived as difficult to incorporate in fisheries management frameworks (Table 2), and very difficult or not relevant to the management of marine mammals.

Potential Gaps & Barriers

We also asked interviewees to discuss potential gaps or barriers to using blue carbon as a metric in addressing climate change and biodiversity loss in Canada, Finland, and the Republic of Korea.

Finland has put forward considerable efforts towards addressing many knowledge and regulatory gaps. Carbon stocks have been estimated for certain marine ecosystems in

Finnish waters, such as eelgrass (*Zostera marina*) or bladderwrack (*Fucus vesiculosus*), but not others (such as blue mussels or reefs). Estimates thus far have indicated that the total amount of carbon is small or not significant. Drivers of degradation (particularly eutrophication, harmful algal blooms) are well understood (particularly at the regional level through [HELCOM](#)), and national regulatory gaps have been identified, but gaps in capacity and resource limitations mean public efforts and funds can be diverted away from addressing specific ecosystems in Finnish jurisdictional waters (see also the entry for Iceland in the [2025 report on NBSAP development](#) from the Nordic Biodiversity Framework, published by the Nordic Council of Ministers) and focus instead on reducing these drivers of degradation that impact multiple ecosystems simultaneously. It was reported that marine ecosystems struggled to have as high of a priority or profile as terrestrial ecosystems in national policies or the political process (especially when compared to forests), and projections of change were also unclear.

Data gaps in blue carbon in the Republic of Korea (ROK) are being specifically assessed in collaborative efforts between the government and universities (as in the EU). However, since “polar blue carbon” lies outside of the traditional coastal ecosystems as defined by IPCC (mangroves, seagrasses, and salt marshes), the perceived knowledge gap instead lies within institutional frameworks at the regulatory level, with different agencies dividing responsibilities and lacking coordination. Limited political or public awareness of non-conventional or emerging carbon-capturing marine habitats was also highlighted. While ecosystem services and benefits from nature are well-known, the gap for the citizens of the ROK and policymakers instead was identified to be in recognizing and understanding the environmental problems and threats from climate change faced by blue carbon ecosystems, in contrast to insights from Finland.

Ministerial mandate letters in Canada provided a clear signal to both public servants and scientists that blue carbon was a priority. But given its enormous geographic area, current ecosystem extent and carbon stock data are still lacking in many Canadian waters, often in high-latitude polar regions. Echoing Finland, drivers of degradation for these marine ecosystems are understood (particularly climate change), but regulatory and governance frameworks need further development (like the Republic of Korea). Available blue carbon data was concentrated mostly in the southernmost coastal areas on the Atlantic and Pacific and focused on certain species (such as eelgrass), with less effort and unknown implications for similar species at higher latitudes. There was also uncertainty about projections of change and the role of blue carbon moving poleward in the future (data on future ecosystem extent or ecosystem functioning).

CONCLUSIONS

Our analysis revealed an apparent lack of coordination to date on blue carbon specifically or marine ecosystems broadly, between national biodiversity and climate plans of the Arctic Council member states, observer countries, and the European Union. While recognizing that a “whole-of-society” or “whole-of-government” approach takes time, future submissions would benefit from more coherent action between climate and biodiversity policy at the national and international levels. For additional guidance, see this [Synergies Checklist](#) (developed by GIZ, IISD, and WWF, 2024).

Our analysis indicates that support for the recognition of blue carbon varies by context, with observer states placing comparatively greater emphasis on it in their submissions. This variation could be linked to factors such as institutional capacity, perceived importance of the ocean, political awareness and prioritization, as well as the extent of marine ecosystems within national jurisdiction.

Climate & Biodiversity

The document analysis showed that, despite fewer available NBSAPs than NDCs, blue carbon is more often recognised in the submissions to the Convention on Biological Diversity (Canada, Japan, and the Republic of Korea) than in submissions to the Paris Agreement (Singapore and the UK). However, both NDC and NBSAP submissions acknowledge the role of scientific evidence and research in developing relevant national action plans and management of carbon sequestration. Interviews further highlighted that biodiversity policies – such as establishing marine protected areas (MPAs) or managing kelp forests – are typically perceived as more straightforward avenues for integrating blue carbon into existing biodiversity frameworks than potential avenues for integrating blue carbon into climate policies, for example, incorporating blue carbon ecosystems into national GHG inventories or NDCs, although there was no consensus.

Differentiation between Coastal & Oceanic Blue Carbon

The analysis of NDCs revealed that neither Singapore nor the United Kingdom, despite acknowledging blue carbon in their NDC 3.0 submission, clearly differentiates between coastal and oceanic blue carbon. This contrasts with NBSAP submissions, where countries mention specific ecosystems when referring to blue carbon, associating it with either coastal or oceanic environments. Notably, Canada is the only country that explicitly acknowledges oceanic carbon in its NBSAP. This was also indicated via interviews, where respondents mentioned or discussed blue carbon in a primarily coastal context. One potential reason could be due to the uncertain geographical extent or jurisdiction of oceanic blue carbon.

Mitigation & Adaptation:

Progress in recognizing some blue carbon ecosystems, supported by the 2013 Supplement to the 2006 IPCC Guidelines for National Greenhouse Gas Inventories: Wetlands ([Wetlands Supplement](#)), has likely raised awareness of marine and coastal ecosystems, including blue carbon, as a climate mitigation measure, as reflected in some NDC submissions. Our document analysis showed countries primarily recognise blue carbon for its mitigation potential, with limited attention to its role in adaptation, with interviews providing some support for this finding. We note that mitigation benefits might be better understood because of available quantification methods, whereas adaptation benefits are described in broader, less specific terms.

Science-Policy Interface

After completing the document analysis and complementary interviews, we wish to highlight one noteworthy science-policy gap. Mapping blue carbon ecosystems and quantifying carbon sequestration in the polar regions at relevant scales is ongoing, and drivers of change are generally understood. However, a lack of consideration for projections of change for blue carbon ecosystems appears to be an emerging gap. Without addressing this, there is a real risk that current information and data will not be timely or accurate enough to be adequately reflected under international frameworks, given the rather slow pace of policy uptake.

Based on these findings, we recommend the following actions to address potential gaps at the science-policy interface:

- i. Open formal and informal dialogues within the Arctic Council forum between member and observer states on a potential blue carbon agenda . For example, developing common approaches to include blue carbon in GHG inventories.
- ii. Develop metrics relevant for NDCs and NBSAPs for both oceanic and coastal blue carbon, keeping national jurisdiction in mind. For example, SEA-Quester is developing a species-specific factor for carbon sequestration relative to biomass, with potential use in fisheries management. For species or habitats beyond national jurisdiction (such as plankton), which frameworks might be better suited to manage these carbon stocks (ISA, CCAMLR, RSCs, RFMOs, BBNJ, et cetera)?
- iii. Acknowledge blue carbon more specifically as an adaptation measure in meeting global adaptation goals of the Paris Agreement. Although widely considered a co-benefit, this seems more theoretical at present. Contextualizing these benefits more explicitly and how they align with the Paris Agreement, especially in comparison to or alongside any mitigation benefits, is important to make adaptation measures practically applicable and fully realize this potential. For example, how can kelp forests reduce vulnerability and build resilience of coastal communities?

- iv. Improve potential synergies between NDCs and NBSAPs. This is particularly relevant for Target 8 in the KMGBF, which currently lacks a headline indicator. This is the only target where our analysis found specific references to blue carbon as a research and development priority (Canada and Republic of Korea). For example, could ecosystem accounting frameworks (UN System for Economic and Ecosystem Accounting or UN-SEEA) scale up to effectively track goals and targets under both conventions?
- v. Update a common research agenda to include best-available projections of change for current and emerging blue carbon ecosystems. Although complicated by multiple drivers of change, over which countries have varying degrees of control (marine heatwaves compared to eutrophication, for example), utilizing IPCC methodologies and emissions scenarios (see model intercomparisons in [Tittenser et al., 2021](#)), or developing governance scenarios that make trade-offs explicit (see [Fesenmeyer et al., 2025](#)) can help adjust priorities even with large uncertainties.

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DISCLAIMER: AI software tools were used for interview transcription, some proofreading tasks, and to compile information (detailed in Appendix B). All AI-generated content was reviewed prior to inclusion. The ideas and conceptualization are original, and no AI tools were used in the writing of this document.

Appendix A: Overview of NDCs and NBSAPs

Country	Date of collection		Document length	Source
	NDC 3.0	NDC 2.0		
Member States				
Denmark		31.03.2025	23 pages	https://unfccc.int/sites/default/files/NDC/2023-10/ES-2023-10-17%20EU%20submission%20NDC%20update.pdf
Norway		31.03.2025	17 pages	https://unfccc.int/sites/default/files/NDC/2022-11/NDC%20Norway_second%20update.pdf
Sweden		31.03.2025	23 pages	https://unfccc.int/sites/default/files/NDC/2023-10/ES-2023-10-17%20EU%20submission%20NDC%20update.pdf
Finland		31.03.2025	23 pages	https://unfccc.int/sites/default/files/NDC/2023-10/ES-2023-10-17%20EU%20submission%20NDC%20update.pdf
Russia		15.04.2025	19 pages	https://unfccc.int/sites/default/files/NDC/2022-06/NDC_RF_eng.pdf
United States of America	31.03.2025		33 pages	https://unfccc.int/sites/default/files/2024-12/United%20States%202035%20NDC.pdf
Canada	31.03.2025		188 pages	https://unfccc.int/sites/default/files/2025-02/Canada%27s%202035%20Nationally%20Determined%20Contribution_ENc.pdf
Iceland		31.03.2025	14 pages	https://unfccc.int/sites/default/files/NDC/2022-06/Iceland_updated_NDC_Submission_Feb_2021.pdf
Observers				
France		31.03.2025	23 pages	https://unfccc.int/sites/default/files/NDC/2023-10/ES-2023-10-17%20EU%20submission%20NDC%20update.pdf
Germany		31.03.2025	23 pages	https://unfccc.int/sites/default/files/NDC/2023-10/ES-2023-10-17%20EU%20submission%20NDC%20update.pdf
Italy		31.03.2025	23 pages	https://unfccc.int/sites/default/files/NDC/2023-10/ES-2023-10-17%20EU%20submission%20NDC%20update.pdf
Japan	31.03.2025		15 pages	https://unfccc.int/sites/default/files/2025-02/Japans%202035-2040%20NDC.pdf
Netherlands		31.03.2025	23 pages	https://unfccc.int/sites/default/files/NDC/2023-10/ES-2023-10-17%20EU%20submission%20NDC%20update.pdf
Poland		31.03.2025	23 pages	https://unfccc.int/sites/default/files/NDC/2023-10/ES-2023-10-17%20EU%20submission%20NDC%20update.pdf
India		31.03.2025	4 pages	https://unfccc.int/sites/default/files/NDC/2022-08/India%20Updated%20First%20Nationally%20Determined%20Contrib.pdf
Republic of Korea		31.03.2025	30 pages	https://unfccc.int/sites/default/files/NDC/2022-06/211223_The%20Republic%20of%20Korea%27s%20Enhanced%20Update%20of%20its%20First%20Nationally%20Determined%20Contribution_211227_editorial%20change.pdf
Singapore	31.03.2025		31 pages	https://unfccc.int/sites/default/files/2025-02/Singapore%20Second%20Nationally%20Determined%20Contribution.pdf
Spain		31.03.2025	23 pages	https://unfccc.int/sites/default/files/NDC/2023-10/ES-2023-10-17%20EU%20submission%20NDC%20update.pdf
Switzerland	31.03.2025		23 pages	https://unfccc.int/sites/default/files/2025-01/Switzerland%20second%20NDC%202031-2035.pdf
The United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland (UK)	31.03.2025		74 pages	https://unfccc.int/sites/default/files/2025-01/UK%27s%202035%20NDC%20ICTU.pdf

European Union		31.03.2025	23 pages	https://unfccc.int/sites/default/files/NDC/2023-10/ES-2023-10-17%20EU%20submission%20NDC%20update.pdf
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Country	Date of collection		Document length	Source
	NBSAP	Status		
Member States				
Denmark	07.04.2025	Final	39 pages	https://api.cbd.int/api/v2013/documents/CFB4C8FC-A569-C501-C40E-C3F3E636AB96/attachments/615967/WEB_ENGLISH_National_handlingsplan_for_biodiv_2024.pdf
Canada	07.04.2025	Approved	181 pages	https://publications.gc.ca/collections/collection_2024/eccc/en4/En4-539-1-2024-eng.pdf
Observers				
France	07.04.2025	Approved	45 pages	https://ort.cbd.int/api/v2013/documents/399B1E5C-EE6C-B6BD-4B67-5207383135D7/attachments/615061/National-Biodiversity-Strategy-2030.pdf
Japan	07.04.2025	Approved	274 pages	https://ort.cbd.int/api/v2013/documents/D16E0D4C-842F-CA51-36FF-A75503567A92/attachments/615510/The%20NBSAP%20of%20Japan%202023-2030.pdf
India	07.04.2025	Approved	208 pages	https://api.cbd.int/api/v2013/documents/8D6F8524-3F89-5B94-FC00-2927C0F47AF9/attachments/616236/INDIA'S%20UPDATED%20NBSAP%20(2024-2030).pdf
Republic of Korea	07.04.2025	Approved	103 pages	https://ort.cbd.int/api/v2013/documents/4253C5E1-E499-ECF9-903C-F2E2EB87B2D7/attachments/615522/The%20ROK's%205th%20National%20Biodiversity%20Strategy(2024-2028)(English%20version).pdf
The United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland (UK)	07.04.2025	Approved	48 pages 7 pages (Annex A)	https://api.cbd.int/api/v2013/documents/AA391CC3-2C98-2C3A-D8D8-29ED0FB26D30/attachments/616906/31_03_2025_UK_NBSAP.pdf https://api.cbd.int/api/v2013/documents/AA391CC3-2C98-2C3A-D8D8-29ED0FB26D30/attachments/616640/UK_NBSAP_Annex_A.pdf
European Union	07.04.2025	Approved	27 pages	https://ort.cbd.int/api/v2013/documents/E7949BA7-ED90-9CEB-283B-5F9ED493F783/attachments/615843/eur-nbsap-v4-en.pdf

Appendix B: Supporting Tables

This information was compiled using ChatGPT (GPT-4o model, OpenAI, accessed July 28, 2025) to assist with data collection and synthesis related to country-level geographic boundaries. The model was prompted to: 1) Retrieve coastline and land border length data for 21 countries and the European Union from publicly available sources, including the World Population Review, CIA World Factbook, NationMaster, Eurostat, and other national government publications (e.g., USGS, Danish Coastal Authority, Indian Ministry of Home Affairs). 2) Calculate each country's total external perimeter as the sum of coastline and land border lengths. 3) Compute the percentage of each country's boundary that is coastline. 4) Classify countries into coastal categories (e.g., ">90%") based on these percentages. 5) Generate Excel formulas for automated classification. The results provided by ChatGPT were manually reviewed and cross-verified against source materials. The model also provided draft language for explanatory sections, citations, and category definitions, but this was not used.

COUNTRY	COASTLINE KM	TOTAL PERIMETER KM	% COAST	DATA SOURCE
ICELAND	4970	4970	100	Wikipedia Geography of Iceland
JAPAN	29751	29751	100	Wikipedia Coastline of Japan, CIA Factbook
SINGAPORE	193	193	100	CIA World Factbook
DENMARK	7300	7368	99	CIA World Factbook, Danish Government
UK AND NORTHERN IRELAND	12429	12789	97	Wikipedia Geography of UK
NORWAY	83281	85823	97	Wikipedia Coastline of Norway, CIA Factbook
CANADA	202080	210973	96	World Population Review, CIA Factbook
FINLAND	31119	33682	92	Wikipedia Geography of Finland
EUROPEAN UNION	65000	78180	83	Aggregated EU Data from Eurostat & CIA Factbook
ITALY	7600	9436	81	Wikipedia Geography of Italy
SPAIN	4964	6881	72	Wikipedia Geography of Spain
NETHERLANDS	1142	1719	66	Wikipedia Geography of Netherlands
FRANCE	5500	8389	66	Wikipedia Geography of France
RUSSIA	37653	57670	65	Wikipedia Geography of Russia, NationMaster
UNITED STATES	19924	31958	62	CIA World Factbook, USGS
SWEDEN	3200	5432	59	Wikipedia Geography of Sweden
REPUBLIC OF KOREA	2413	4288	56	Wikipedia Geography of South Korea
CHINA	14500	36617	39.6	CIA World Factbook, Wikipedia Geography of China
GERMANY	2389	6103	39	Wikipedia Geography of Germany
INDIA	7516	21619	35	CIA World Factbook, Indian Government Data
POLAND	770	3285	23	Wikipedia Geography of Poland
SWITZERLAND	0	1852	0	CIA World Factbook

Blue carbon in **NDCs** of the members and observers to the Arctic Council, including the European Union

	Country	Member	Observer	Other	Coastline <90%	Coastline <50-90%	Coastline <0-50%	Unknown	Mention	Do not mention
	Denmark									
	Norway									
	Sweden									
	Finland									
	Russia									
	United States									
	Canada									
	Iceland									
	France									
	Germany									
	Italy									
	Japan									
	Netherlands									
	China									
	Poland									
	India									
	Republic of Korea									
	Singapore									
	Spain									
	Switzerland									
	UK									
	European Union									
Total										
I. Status	22	8	13	1						
	100%	36.3%	59%	4.5%						
II. Coastline	22				8	9	5			
	100%				36.3%	40.9%	22.7%			
III. Acknowledgement	22							1	2	19
	100%							4.5%	9%	86.3%

Blue carbon in **NBSAPs** of the members and observers to the Arctic Council, including the European Union

	Country	Member	Observer	Other	Coastline <90%	Coastline <50-90%	Coastline <0-50%	Not available	Unknown	Mention	Do not mention
	Denmark										
	Norway										
	Sweden										
	Finland										
	Russia										
	United States										
	Canada										
	Iceland										
	France										
	Germany										
	Italy										
	Japan										
	Netherlands										
	China										
	Poland										
	India										
	Republic of Korea										
	Singapore										
	Spain										
	Switzerland										
	UK										
	European Union										
Total											
I. Status	22	8	13	1							
	100%	36.3%	59%	4.5%							
II. Coastline	22				8	9	5				
	100%				36.3%	40.9%	22.7%				
III. Acknowledgement	22							7	7	3	5
	100%							31.8%	31.8%	13.6%	22.7%

Ocean in **NDCs** of the members and observers to the Arctic Council, including the European Union

	Country	Member	Observer	Other	Coastline <90%	Coastline <50-90%	Coastline <0-50%	Unknown	Mention	Do not mention
	Denmark									
	Norway									
	Sweden									
	Finland									
	Russia									
	United States									
	Canada									
	Iceland									
	France									
	Germany									
	Italy									
	Japan									
	Netherlands									
	China									
	Poland									
	India									
	Republic of Korea									
	Singapore									
	Spain									
	Switzerland									
	UK									
	European Union									
Total										
I. Status	22	8	13	1						
	100%	36.3%	59%	4.5%						
II. Coastline	22				8	9	5			
	100%				36.3%	40.9%	22.7%			
III. Acknowledgement	22							1	5	16
	100%							4.5%	22.7%	72.7%

Ocean in **NBSAPs** of the members and observers to the Arctic Council, including the European Union

	Country	Member	Observer	Other	Coastline <90%	Coastline <50-90%	Coastline <0-50%	Not available	Unknown	Mention	Do not mention
	Denmark										
	Norway										
	Sweden										
	Finland										
	Russia										
	United States										
	Canada										
	Iceland										
	France										
	Germany										
	Italy										
	Japan										
	Netherlands										
	China										
	Poland										
	India										
	Republic of Korea										
	Singapore										
	Spain										
	Switzerland										
	UK										
	European Union										
Total											
I. Status	22	8	13	1							
	100%	36.3%	59%	4.5%							
II. Coastline	22				8	9	5				
	100%				36.3%	40.9%	22.7%				
III. Acknowledgement	22							7	7	8	0
	100%							31.8%	31.8%	36.3%	

Appendix C: Survey Instrument*

*Questions were adjusted within and between interviews to based on interviewee feedback. See Methods for more details.

General Background

This section identifies the stakeholder group and background of the person being interviewed.

CATEGORY CHOICE: How would you describe your current occupation/sector of work?

National Government / Sub-National Government / Intergovernmental Organization / Indigenous Peoples Organization / Local Management / Non-Profit or NGO / Other

OPEN: How many years have you been working in this field?

OPEN: Which countries/regions are you evaluating today?

OPEN: How have you been involved in the application of or discussions about blue carbon and marine management in this country or region? This could include policy development, scientific research, conservation efforts, stakeholder engagement, or other relevant activities.

Perception of the Marine Environment

This section identifies a baseline for views on the state of the marine environment.

“Very Good” means minimal degradation, stable, or improving conditions.

“Fair” indicates that some degradation is present but is still functioning.

“Poor” indicates significant degradation, with major concerns about ecosystem integrity.

“Don’t Know” indicates there is insufficient data or lack expertise/confidence to adequately assess the current state of the marine environment.

SCALE CHOICE: How would you characterize the general condition of the coastal marine environment in your country/region?

very good / fair / poor / don’t know

SCALE CHOICE: How would you characterize the general condition of the pelagic marine environment in your country/region and areas beyond national jurisdiction?

very good / fair / poor / don’t know

SCALE CHOICE: How would you characterize the general condition of the benthic marine environment in your country/region and areas beyond national jurisdiction?

very good / fair / poor / don’t know

Engagement Level (Ambition/Commitment Gap)

This section identifies the current level of political will or ambition to incorporate blue carbon into various policy instruments.

SCALE CHOICE: Which best describes your understanding of the current level of political engagement towards blue carbon ecosystems in your country/region?

- Extent of blue carbon ecosystems in the country is unknown or poorly understood
- The potential role of blue carbon for carbon mitigation or adaptation is unclear
- Institutional arrangements for polar blue carbon are uncertain or conflicted
- Institutional arrangements for polar blue carbon are clear and policies are under development
- Institutional arrangements for polar blue carbon are clear
- Don't know / No clear information available

OPEN: Can you provide more details about why this is the case?

For example, which governmental agencies are responsible for management of blue carbon ecosystems or parts of these ecosystems? Are these ecosystems managed through environmental development approvals, or for fisheries? Does the private sector have any data or undertake any management actions? Do port developers undertake environmental assessments of these ecosystems?

Knowledge Level (Data & Implementation Gaps)

This section identifies the current level of knowledge on the location, extent, and condition of polar blue carbon ecosystems within a country/region.

SCALE CHOICE: What best describes your understanding of the current level of understanding of polar blue carbon ecosystems in your country/region?

Ecosystem extent AND carbon stocks largely or partially unknown

Ecosystem extent known but specific carbon stock assessments missing

Ecosystem extent known and carbon stock data available, but countrywide projections of change** are unclear

Drivers of degradation** and loss are not well understood, but regulatory impact unclear

Drivers of degradation and loss are well understood, but regulatory and governance frameworks are not adequately understood

Drivers of degradation and loss are well understood, and regulatory gaps identified

Policies, regulations, and targets to reduce degradation rates or threats to blue carbon ecosystems are in place, and monitoring gaps identified

Systems to monitor drivers of degradation and loss & enforcement in place

Significant research efforts are underway, but findings are still preliminary or unpublished.

OPEN: Does the level of knowledge vary by area? If so, please explain.

OPEN: Which knowledge gaps (scientific, regulatory, or both) do you see as the most significant? If drivers of degradation are unclear, what are the main suspected causes (e.g., pollution, coastal development, climate change)?

For example, if drivers are not well understood, is there any knowledge about the relative contributions of degradation from pollution/eutrophication coastal development, climate change? Or economic pressures? If drivers are well understood, which are the most significant, in their view? Can regulatory frameworks and ecosystem extent be identified in parallel?

Co-Benefits and Impacts

This section aims to identify potential co-benefits and impacts from the application of polar blue carbon.

SCALE CHOICE: Recognition of the value of Polar Blue Carbon ecosystems can help climate change adaptation efforts within my country/region.

5 = strongly agree, 4 agree, 3 neither agree or disagree, 2 disagree, 1 strongly disagree

SCALE CHOICE: Recognition of the value of Polar Blue Carbon can help improve marine based food security (small-scale or commercial) within my country/region.

5 = strongly agree, 4 agree, 3 neither agree or disagree, 2 disagree, 1 strongly disagree
(small-scale fisheries & nursery habitats for commercial fisheries)

SCALE CHOICE: Recognition of the value of Polar Blue Carbon ecosystems can help the private sector (aquaculture or seaweed farming) within my country/region.

5 = strongly agree, 4 agree, 3 neither agree or disagree, 2 disagree, 1 strongly disagree

SCALE CHOICE: Recognition of the value of Polar Blue Carbon ecosystems can help increase marine biodiversity within my country/region.

5 = strongly agree, 4 agree, 3 neither agree or disagree, 2 disagree, 1 strongly disagree

SCALE CHOICE: Recognition of the value of Polar Blue Carbon ecosystems can help increase marine based tourism or personal recreational use within my country/region.

5 = strongly agree, 4 agree, 3 neither agree or disagree, 2 disagree, 1 strongly disagree

SCALE CHOICE: Recognition of the cultural and social values of Polar Blue Carbon ecosystems can help my country/region.

5 = strongly agree, 4 agree, 3 neither agree or disagree, 2 disagree, 1 strongly disagree

OPEN: Did we miss any co-benefits?

OPEN: Can you foresee any negative consequences from the application of Polar Blue Carbon in your country/region?

Overall Assessment

This section aims to assess overall difficulty of incorporating polar blue carbon into various policies and frameworks at the EU, international, regional, or national level.

How relevant is the value of Polar Blue Carbon to the following marine management and ocean policies within your country/region?

	Highly Relevant	Somewhat Relevant	Not Relevant	Unsure / Don't Know
Fisheries management (designating catch limits, seasonal regulations)				
Management of important marine benthic habitats				
Management of kelp forests				
Management of marine mammals / biodiversity beyond national jurisdiction				
National biodiversity plans (e.g., NBSAP, others)				
Management / Establishment of Marine Protected Areas (MPAs)				
National climate policies (e.g. National GHG Inventories, NDCs)				
Coastal zone management or marine spatial planning (MSP)				
EU reporting & compliance, if applicable (MSFD, LULUCF, Restoration Law)				
OPEN: Other regional, national, or sub-national policies?				

SCALE CHOICE: IF highly OR somewhat relevant, how difficult will it be to incorporate the value of polar blue carbon into those marine management and ocean policies within your country/region?

	Very Difficult	Somewhat Difficult	Easy	Unsure / Don't Know
Fisheries Management (designating catch limits, seasonal regulations)				
Management of Important Marine Benthic Habitats				
Management of Kelp Forests				
Management of Marine Mammals or other Biodiversity Beyond National Jurisdiction				
National Biodiversity Plans (NBSAP, EU Restoration Plans)				
Management / Establishment of Marine Protected Areas (MPAs)				
National Climate Policies (National GHG Inventories, NDCs)				
Coastal Zone Management or Marine Spatial Planning (MSP)				
EU reporting & compliance, if applicable (MSFD, LULUCF, Restoration Law)				
OPEN: Other national or sub-national policies & management?				

OPEN: For policies where integration is difficult, what are the key obstacles (e.g., lack of political will, insufficient regulatory framework, competing economic interests)?

OPEN: Do you see any conflicts between existing policies that could make incorporating Polar Blue Carbon more difficult?

OPEN: Did you have any other comments or concerns you wanted to pass along to our scientific community?